

Quantum Entropy and Thermodynamics

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In the literature, one often sees entropy density expressions of the form: $- [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ ((1)) (1). In a recent note (2), we suggested entropy density may be written as: $-W \times d/dx W - a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]$ ((2)). In this note, we wish to compare these two expressions with the thermodynamic equation: $dE = TdS - PdV$. Thus, an expression for temperature must first be found. We use the hydrodynamical equation: $T = m/3 \langle |v-u|^*|v-u \rangle$ and find that $T(x) = 1/m \{ -d/dx d/dx W / W + [dW/dx / W][dW/dx / W] \}$ in one-dimension. Thus, temperature is a function of x except for the ground state oscillator case i.e. $W(x) = \sqrt{B} \exp(-ax^2)$ where $a = .5 \sqrt{km}$ and $B = \sqrt{km/3.14}$. In this case, temperature is constant in space. We consider this situation, and find that expression ((1)) yields dE/T not equal to dS and ((2)) $dE = T dS$ for the ground state oscillator, if one varies k , the spring constant.

Temperature for a Quantum Bound State

We use the hydrodynamic expression (3):

$$T = .333m \langle |v-u|^*|v-u \rangle = 1/m \{ -d/dx d/dx W / W + [dW/dx / W][dW/dx / W] \} \quad ((3))$$

We replace .333 with 1 in the 1 dimensional situation.

In a previous note (4), we found that a bound quantum system with $m = .5$ satisfies the momentum conservation hydrodynamic equation for which:

$$\text{Pressure} = P = \text{density} \langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle = W(x) \{ -d/dx d/dx W / W + [dW/dx / W][dW/dx / W] \} \quad ((4))$$

Here we use $\text{density} = W(x)$ for a bound quantum state. In (2), we argued one may apply hydrodynamics by using $W(x)$ and not $W^*(x)W(x)$ as density.

From ((4)), one sees that the ideal gas law applies i.e. $P = W(x) T$ where again $W(x)$ is used as density.

From ((3)), one sees that quantum bound state temperature is a function of x . In one special case, however, it becomes a constant, namely that of a quantum oscillator ground state for which $W(x) = \sqrt{B} \exp(-ax^2)$ where $a = .5\sqrt{km}$. In such a case:

$$T = \sqrt{k/m} \quad ((5))$$

One may note that even though $W(x)W(x)$ is of the same form as the classical statistical result $\exp(-.5kx^2/T)$ for an oscillator, the classical and quantum temperature values differ.

dE/T for the Ground State Oscillator

$E = \sqrt{k/m}(n+.5)$ for an oscillator so for the ground state case: $E = .5 \sqrt{k/m}$. ((6))

If one decides to vary E by varying k, the spring constant, then: $dE = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{1/m} k^{-1/2}$ ((7))

Thus: $dE/T = 1/(4k)$. This must next be compared with the result for dS.

dS for S density = $-[W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$

Often in the literature, one finds entropy density written as (1):

S density = $-[W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - [a(p)a(p)] \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ ((8))

For the ground state oscillator: $W(x) = \sqrt{B} \exp(-axx)$ where $B = \sqrt{2a/3}$.14 and $a = .5 \sqrt{k/m}$.

Thus: $-\int dx [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] = \int dx \exp(-2axx) B \{ [2axx] + \ln(B) \}$ ((9))

The first term is not a function of k because it goes as $2a^{1/2}/2a$.

The second term is a function of k, i.e. $\ln(B)$ because $B \int dx \exp(-2axx) = 1$ and so:

$d/dk \ln(B) = 1/B dB/dk = 1/(4k)$ ((10))

Following (1), we use relationships which incorporate the normalization used for a(p):

$S_x = A + \ln(\text{sig}_x)$ and $S_p = A + \ln(\text{sig}_p)$ where A is an integral given in (1), $\text{sig}_x = \sqrt{1/(wm)}$ and $\text{sig}_p = \sqrt{wm}$ where $w = \sqrt{k/m}$.

Thus: $S_p = S_x - \ln(\text{sig}_x) + \ln(\text{sig}_p) = S_x + .5 \ln(km)$ ((11))

So: $dS_p/dk = 1/(4k) + .5/k$ ((12))

Thus, $dS = dS_k + dS_p = 1/k$ ((13))

This does not satisfy $dE = TdS$.

$$dS \text{ for } S_{\text{density}} = -W \times dW/dx - a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]$$

For the expression for entropy density we propose:

$$S \text{ density} = -W \times dW/dx - [a(-p)a(p)] \ln[a(-p)a(p)] \quad ((12))$$

The x integral of the first term yields 1, so it is not dependent on k, the spring constant. For the case of a(p), one must be careful regarding normalization. From (5), we use:

$$W(x) = \int F(p)/(2\pi\hbar) \exp(ipx) dp \text{ so } a(p) = F(p)/(2\pi\hbar)$$

$$a(p)2\pi\hbar = \int f(x)/(2\pi\hbar) \exp(-ipx) dx$$

$$W(x) = \sqrt{B} \exp(-a x^2) \text{ so } a(p)2\pi\hbar = \sqrt{B} \sqrt{2\pi\hbar} 1/\sqrt{2a} \exp(-p^2/4a) \text{ so:}$$

$$a(p) = \exp(-p^2/4a) (a2\pi\hbar)^{-1/4}$$

The normalization needed for $\exp(-p^2/2a)$ (i.e. from $a(p)a(p)$) is: $C = 1/\sqrt{2\pi\hbar} 1/\sqrt{2a}$

The integral is:

$$(1/C) C \int dp \exp(-p^2/2a) 1/\sqrt{a2\pi\hbar} \{ -p^2/2a - .5 \ln(a2\pi\hbar) \}$$

The first term does not depend on k, the spring constant, only the second so:

$$d/dk (-1/2 \ln(a)) = d/dk [-2 \cdot 1/2 \ln(k)] = -1/(4k) \quad ((13))$$

This result matches dE/T so the entropy density from (2) applied to the case of the ground state oscillator satisfies the thermodynamic relationship $dE = TdS$ with V held constant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present a formula for temperature in a 1 dimensional quantum bound state, namely: $1/m \{ -d/dx d/dx W / W + [dW/dx / W][dW/dx / W] \}$. From this we conclude that temperature is a function of x except for the ground state of an oscillator for which it is constant. In this case, we try to evaluate $dE = T dS$ (with volume held fixed) for two entropy formulae. The first is an entropy density often given in the literature, namely: $- [W^*W] \ln[W^*W] - a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$. The second is an entropy density which we have proposed, namely: $-W \times d/dx W - a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]$. We find that for the first case, dE/T does not equal dS , but that it does in the latter for the ground state oscillator.

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